

DWR mixed crops and hispa incidence ($r = -0.509$, $p < 0.05$, $df = 14$), but positive in the case of the long-horned cricket ($r = 0.76$, $p < 0.01$, $df = 14$).

The change in cropping pattern (increased MV boro rice cropping in DWR areas) positively influenced YSB and probably also favored hispa. Boro cropping favored the establishment of first generation YSB moths (following diapause in winter) in boro rice during Feb and Mar. Irrigated boro cropping

also reduced or eliminated high temperature stress ($>33^\circ\text{C}$) coupled with low relative humidity ($<70\%$) on the YSB during Apr-Jun, which favored population buildup.

YSB seems to concentrate in DWR following boro rice harvest. Hispa prefers young rice plants. That explains its concentration in fields with only DWR. Ripening aus rice probably influenced the high incidence of long-horned crickets in aus rice + DWR fields. ■

Dispersal range of rice insect pests under natural conditions in the Philippines

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We estimated the dispersal range of rice insect pests in the Philippines using a low-cost method that measures rather than manipulates natural movement. Conventional approaches (such as mark-recapture) often require handling the insects in ways that could significantly affect behavior.

During the fallow period between wet and dry season crops in early 1982, we located an isolated 1.5-ha field in Nueva Ecija where IR52 had been grown under irrigation from a shallow well pump. Except for a similar field one km west, this field had the only standing rice within several kilometers.

As the crop approached maturity, we established two parallel transects of kerosene light traps running eastward, 200 m apart. The traps were positioned within the field and at 5, 20, 50, 95, 170, 290, and 485 m into the fallow area, a geometric progression that provided greatest resolution near the field. The lamps were lit every night for more than a month, until harvest in late February.

We analyzed catches of *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *Paraponyx fluctuosalis*, and *Naranga aenescens* from 19 Jan until they began to rise after the fallow area was planted (see table). Catches of other species were too low to analyze.

The best-fitting first- or second-degree nonlinear equations are given in the table and illustrated for yellow stem borer (YSB) males in the figure. Catches declined with distance from the field. Dispersal distances were calculated from regressions corrected for background density (i.e., insects emerging from rice stubble, other host plants, and distant, scattered sources). We estimated background density from catches in four light traps at two sites 4.5 km to the east and the south. Corrected equations were integrated and rotated about the origin (in other words, assuming that movement was similar in all directions).

Toxicology of insecticides to rice leaffolder (LF) larvae

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We evaluated the toxicology of three commonly used insecticides: an organophosphate, a carbamate, and a synthetic pyrethroid. Fourth-instar LF

Cnaphalocrocis medinalis larvae from cultures reared from moths collected in Laguna, Philippines, were topically treated at 15 d old with 0.5 μl of each insecticide solution, using an Arnold Microapplicator. Control larvae were treated with acetone.

Results are given in the table. The probit lines fitted the data well, and the insects used were found to be homogeneous.

In the test for parallelism, probit lines for BPMC and cypermethrin were found to

be parallel; diazinon significantly deviated from these two lines (see figure). The parallel lines satisfy the condition of similarity and are thus comparable.

Cypermethrin was about 250 times more toxic than BPMC. This implies that a much smaller dose of cypermethrin is required to cause LF mortality.

These results can be used as baseline data for insecticide resistance studies. ■

Probit lines of insecticides topically applied on the fourth-instar leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* larvae.

Probit analysis of diazinon, BPMC, and cypermethrin on 4th-instar larvae of rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*.

Insecticide	LC ₅₀ (ppm)	Fiducial limits (ppm)	LD ₅₀ ($\mu\text{g/larva}$)	Regression equation
Diazinon	259.8	215.5 - 310.1	0.13	$y = 5.07 + 2.70(x-12.44)$
BPMC	9896.6	6519.1 - 15264.4	4.95	$y = 4.91 + 0.95(x-13.97)$
Cypermethrin	40.6	23.0 - 141.1	0.02	$y = 4.83 + 1.11(x-11.46)$

Rice whorl maggot (RWM) incidence in Assam

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In May 1990, RWM *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino was observed to attack

traditional rice variety Maibi sown 20 Mar 1990 as summer rainfed rice on a 15-20% slope in the hill district of Karbi Anglong, Assam. This is the first report of RWM attacking rice in upland fields. The insect has been recorded earlier on rice crops in the plains and low-lying areas. ■

Equations^d relating light trap catches of rice-feeding insects to distance from an isolated field, and estimated dispersal distances. Nueva Ecija, Philippines, Jan-Feb 1982.

	YSB males	YSB females	<i>P. fluctuosalis</i>	<i>N. aenescens</i>
Period	19/1 - 16/2	19/1 - 16/2	19/1 - 12/2	19/11 - 8/2
Best-fitting equation	$Y = 87.0 - 5.74 \ln(X + 0.5)$	$Y = 48.1 + 33.0 \ln(X + 0.5) - 2.72 \ln(X + 0.5)^2$	$Y = 11.0 \exp(-0.002 X)$	$Y = 6.83 \exp(-0.003 X)$
F	9.45*	11.7*	4.77*	5.08*
R ² 0.53		0.59	0.27	0.39
Equation corrected for background density	$Y = 40.0 - 5.74 \ln(X + 0.5)$	$Y = 43.6 + 33.0 \ln(X + 0.5) - 2.72 \ln(X + 0.5)^2$	$Y = 8.59 \exp(-0.003 X)$	$Y = 6.35 \exp(-0.006 X)$
R ² 0.53	0.59		0.29	0.39
Estimated dispersal distances (km):				
50% of population	0.46	0.76	0.64	0.27
80% of population	0.70	1.10	1.10	0.47

^a Y = total catch during the indicated period, X = distance from the field edge. * = P < 0.05. YSB = yellow stem borer.

Dispersal may have been underestimated because the transects were oriented to the prevailing wind. On the other hand, dispersal from a field planted in synchrony with surrounding areas

probably would have been lower, because insects would fly over potential habitat rather than over barren ground. Dispersal estimates are sensitive to the assumed background density, but catches at the

Catch of YSB in kerosene light traps 19 Jan-16 Feb 1982, in relation to distance from the edge of an isolated field planted out of season. The curve is the uncorrected equation given in the table.

traps used to calculate background density were low and uniform for all but YSB males.

The median dispersal distances we found are similar to indices of dispersal derived from the correlation of seasonal abundance as measured in light traps, and the duration of the rice crop in the vicinity (described elsewhere). ■

Rice yellow stem borer (YSB) egg deposition preferences

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We studied preference of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) moths for egg deposition on deepwater rice (DWR) during the first week of Jul 1988. YSB moth populations were very high in Rajbari, Gazipur (a DWR research site). We counted the egg masses on four randomly selected lines out of 12, each 5 m long, in a regional yield trial.

BR4112-2B-6 and DWC-B-184 had significantly fewer egg masses (Table 1). Plant height, leaf blade width, and foliage color did not correlate with number of egg masses.

In 1989, we tested apparent nonpreference for egg deposition on these DWR entries in a pot experiment in the nethouse, in a completely randomized design with eight replications. Three of the less preferred and two of the highly preferred entries were exposed for 2 d at maximum tillering to about 300 female moths. Egg masses deposited and tiller

Table 1. Yellow stem borer egg masses deposited on deepwater rice^a entries at early elongation stage. Rajbari, Gazipur, Bangladesh, July 1988.

Line	Replications (no.)	Foliage color	Plant height (cm)	Leaf blade width (mm)	Egg mass density ^b (no./4 rows)
BR4112-2B-6	3	Pale green	128.9	7.8	1.0 e
DWC-B-184	3	Deep green	139.8	8.7	1.3 e
Habiganj Aman II	3	Pale green	118.3	6.5	2.7 de
BR311-B-5-4	4	Pale green	108.7	6.5	3.0 cde
Sadapankaich	4	Pale green	115.2	6.8	3.2 cde
BR516-48-3	3	Green	131.4	7.2	3.3 bcde
BR308-B-2-4	4	Green	115.5	6.1	3.5 bcde
Kartiksail	4	Green	109.0	7.9	3.5 bcde
BR683-65-4-1-1 (c)	3	Pale green	108.8	6.6	3.7 bcde
DWC-B-14-1-x-6	4	Green	107.7	6.3	3.7 bcde
Habiganj Aman I	4	Pale green	110.9	6.2	3.7 bcde
BR683-65-4-1-1 (M)	3	Deep green	99.4	8.1	4.0 bcde
BR4112-2B-9	3	Green	130.4	6.7	4.0 bcde
Habiganj Aman IV	4	Green	105.9	6.4	4.7 bcd
Kartiksail-HR8	4	Green	105.4	6.4	5.0 bcd
BR306-B-3-2-HR46	3	Green	136.4	6.8	5.0 bcd
IR11185-0-0-0-88-2	3	Green	133.4	7.1	5.0 bcd
BR224-2B-2-5	4	Green	115.9	6.2	5.2 bcd
BR4112-2B-2	3	Green	126.8	6.7	5.7 bcd
BR4112-2B-7	3	Green	126.6	8.0	6.0 abc
IR33708-2B-1	3	Green	119.4	6.7	6.3 ab
Sadapankaich-HR40	3	Green	122.5	6.6	6.3 ab
BR4112-2B-5	3	Pale green	125.5	7.4	9.0 a

^a Water depth varied from 35 to 55 cm on different plots. ^b Counted on 4 of 12 rows each 5 m long, in 3- × 5-m plots. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

density were counted and average plant height measured.

BR4112-2B-6 and Habiganj Aman II, two of the less preferred entries in the field, had significantly fewer egg masses

than did highly preferred Sadapankaich-HR40 (Table 2). DWC-B-184, which was less preferred in the field, had about the same number of egg masses as the highly preferred entries. ■